

The Impact of the Use of the Lector Application on the Subject of Studying the Work of SMPN 3 Pitu Riase

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ABSTRACT

This study uses a quantitative method with the type of experimental research aimed at testing the "Effect of the Use of Lectora Applications on the Learning Results of Students of Class VIII UPT State High School 3 Pitu Riase". The population of 30 students with Sampling technique using saturated sampling or total samplings. This research variable has two, namely, the free variable Impact of Application Usage of Lectora(X) and its bound variable is the Study Results of Students of Grade VIII of the State High School 3 Pitu Riase (y), this research is carried out at the UPT of State High school 3 Putu Riase. Based on the data analysis, we obtained a value of $X=81.93 > Y$ value =70,06 so it can be known that there is an impact of the use of the application of the lecturer on the learning outcome of the students of the eighth grade of the secondary school of the State of 3rd grade. Based upon the results of the research, it is possible to conclude that the impact of using the application for lecturers on the study outcomes of the student of the 8th grade of UPT of the third grade, it shows that the hypothesis of the work stating that there are effects of the Use of the Application of Lectors on the Students of the 3rd degree of the UPT, is acceptable.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a conscious and planned effort to create an atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble morals, and skills needed by themselves, society, nation and state (Dwi Siswoyo, et al. ., 2007). Apart from that, education is a means of developing and improving the quality of human resources (Kamal et al., 2022) . Education has an important role in human life, therefore Islam, as a religion of mercy, gives serious attention to the development of education for human survival (Sari et al., 2021) .According to Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble morals, and the skills needed by themselves and society , nation and state (Inkiriwang et al., nd).

Larlen (2013) in (Sari et al., 2021) stated that education cannot be separated from the teaching and learning process. Interaction will occur between educators and students, where the interaction process will continue to exist in the learning process. The success of an education can be determined by several components including: teachers, students, curriculum, teaching materials, learning media and learning methods. The use of learning media in the teaching and learning process will shift the teacher's position as the main source of information to become a facilitator for students both inside and outside the classroom. The media used in learning is primarily to generate interest in learning, stimulate students, motivate students to play an active role in learning. It is hoped that the use of media can make it easier to convey the material provided and can improve the quality of learning (Sari et al., 2021) . To create a multimedia learning environment that can stimulate students' thoughts, feelings, attention and interest, the author tries to implement learning using the Lectora application on the craft learning outcomes of Class VII Students at SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase.

In line with the above, it is best that when using interactive learning media, teachers are not limited to just mastering Microsoft Power Point. The researcher made further observations through interviews with the Crafts subject teacher for class VIII students at SMP Negeri Pitu Riase. In reality, when the learning process takes place, teachers rarely use technology-based learning media because teachers are only limited in being able to operate Microsoft Power Point. Other learning media used by teachers in the classroom are textbooks and blackboards, so that students are less focused on understanding the material presented by the teacher. Therefore, there is a need for supporting media such as displaying images, videos and educational games to make it easier for students to understand the material in textbooks and students do not feel bored when studying.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Influence is an activity or example that either directly or indirectly results in a change in people's behavior and attitudes. According to the Big

Indonesian Dictionary, "Influence is an attraction that exists or arises from something (person or object) which helps shape a person's character, beliefs or actions (Rahayu & Sidiqin, 2019) .

Understanding Media

The word media comes from the Latin *medius* which literally means "middle", "intermediary" or "introduction". Teaching media is defined as anything that can be used to convey messages or lesson content, stimulate students' thoughts, feelings, attention and abilities, so that they can encourage the teaching and learning process (Abdul Wahid, 2018) . In this sense, teachers, books, texts and the school environment are media. More specifically, the definition of media in the teaching and learning process tends to be defined as graphic, photographic or electronic tools for capturing, processing and reassembling visual or verbal information (Nugrahani & Rupa, 2017) .

Lectora was developed by Trivantis Corporation which is an Authoring Tool for developing e-learning content . The founder was Timothy D. Loudermilk in Cincinnati, Ohio, America in 1999 (Muhammad Mas'ud, 2012). In 2000, Lectora became the first AICC-certified authoring system on the market. Lectora can be used to combine flash, record video, combine images, and screen capture. Lectora is designed specifically for beginners, so the advantage of Lectora is that it is very easy to use in creating learning media and can create test or evaluation materials. Teachers who are not very skilled at operating computers will easily use this application. By using the Lectora application program we can use it to prepare teaching materials for students (Rahmawati & Isroah, 2013) .

Muhammad Mas'ud (2012) In (Khasanah, 2017) The use of Lectora media is very suitable for learning activities, because Lectora media is not only easy to use but also interactive and contains material. which is not just text, but images, animation, video and sound. In this way, students will find it easier to understand the material and make students not get bored quickly. Apart from that, in Lectora media too There are tests that can be done immediately and then the results will be available immediately It is known that students have finished working on all the questions. The form of the test too varies, including multiple choice, true-false, matching, short description, and essays. The existence of tests in Lectora media will help students in learning evaluation activities, so that it will grow students' motivation to.

Craft learning results for class VIII students at SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase will increase with the application of learning media, because the presence of media can develop students' thinking patterns in learning. One way is by using the Lectora application , with the Lectora application Students are expected to be able to develop skills in using increasingly developing computer technology.

Research must be prepared using a systematic method, namely going through several stages. Formulating a hypothesis is the third step in research after presenting a framework for thinking and theoretical basis. From the description here it is clear that a hypothesis is a temporary answer to the problem that has been studied. In this case, the allegations submitted are wrong, they will be rejected, and if they are true, they will be accepted, before

the author conducts research to determine whether or not there is an effect of the application. Lectora on the Craft Learning Results of Class VII I Students of SMPN 3 Pitu Riase, then this hypothesis is put forward, namely:

Ha: There is an influence of using the Lectora application on the craft learning outcomes of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase

Ho: There is no effect on using the application Lectora on Craft Learning Results of Class VIII Students of SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase.

METHODOLOGY

In this research, researchers will use a quantitative approach. Quantitative is research that requires a lot of use of numbers, starting from data collection, interpretation of the data, and the appearance of the results (Leviasari, 2021) . This research uses a type of experimental research which aims to test the effect of using the Canva application on the craft learning outcomes of class VII students at SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase.

According to (Sugiyono 2015: 107) Experimental research is research that requires researchers to control or manipulate one or more independent variables and observe the dependent variable, to see the differences or research that looks at the causal relationship between these two variables. Research variables are basically anything in any form that is applied by the researcher to study so that information about it is obtained, then conclusions are drawn.

In this research, researchers used two variables, namely:

1. The independent variable (X) in this research is the use of Lectora as a tool in the learning process.
2. The dependent variable (Y) in this research is the results of learning Natural Sciences at SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase.

The operational definition of a variable is the definition of a variable by categorizing its properties into elements that can be measured. To provide an explanation of the variables selected in the research. The following will provide operational definitions of the variables used in the research. According to (Sugiyono, 2013) The sample is part of the number and characteristics of the population. If the population is large, and it is impossible for researchers to study everything in the population, for example due to limited funds , energy and time, then researchers can use samples taken from that population. What is learned from the sample, the conclusions can be applied to the population. For this reason, samples taken from the population must be truly representative.

The sampling technique used was saturated sampling. Sample selection technique when all members of the population are sampled. The sampling technique in this study used a saturated sampling technique, where the entire population in this study was sampled.

Table 1. Conditions of the Research Sample

No	Class	L	P	Amount
1	VIII A	5	10	15
2	VIII B	7	8	15
	Amount	12	18	30

Source : SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase

So the sample in this study was 36 students from class VIII SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase. The sample results were divided into two groups, namely, experimental and control.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research was carried out in classes VII IA and VIII B. These classes is a sample from class VII I UPT SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase which was selected. In study Which has held shared become 2 group that is group experiment in process activity learning will use Lectora and groups control in the process Learning Activities No using Lectora. After carrying out the second learning process group the given test.

Presentation Data

Based on results study Which done with use documentation and multiple choice tests as data collection instruments, then obtained results as following:

1. Data variable X, is data results Study Crafts Which use Lectora (Group Experiment)
2. Data variable Y, is data Craft learning outcomes Which No use Lectora (Group Control).

To facilitate the analysis process, the collected data will first be presented, then analyzed, then continued with hypothesis testing using statistical techniques as in table 4.1.

Table 2. Scores and Values of Experimental Group Craft learning outcomes

No	Sample Code	Score	Mark
1	AF	24	80
2	E	21	70
3	HA	21	70
4	HS	24	80
5	HE	23	76
6	JA	26	86
7	K	28	93
8	m	22	73
9	MR	28	93
10	M.A	27	90
11	m	25	83
12	R	25	83
13	R.I	28	93
14	S.N	25	83
15	Z	23	76

Source: Student Project

From the results of craft learning in the Experimental Group above, it shows that no student got a score of 100. The highest score was 93 then the lowest score was 70. Furthermore, table 4.2 below presents the project results obtained by the control group of class VII I UPT SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase students.

Table 3. Scores and Values of Control Group Craft learning outcomes

No	Sample Code	Score	Mark
1	AD	21	70
2	AH	19	63
3	AL	20	66
4	E	22	73
5	I	19	63
6	KH	23	76
7	M.G	20	66
8	N	20	66
9	NS	24	80
10	R.A	23	76
11	RS	25	83
12	SS	19	63
13	BC	21	70
14	W	22	73
15	YK	19	63

Source: Student Project

Based on table 4.2 of the control group above, the highest score obtained was 80 and the lowest score was 63. The aim of this research is to find out whether the Lectora application has an effect on the learning outcomes of class VIII students at UPT SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase, by taking samples from 30 students of class VIII SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase. Students from the experimental and control groups were identified using a saturated sampling method.

Results from the experimental group using the Lectora application on process study obtain mark which is more tall compared to with control group who did not use the Lectora application during the learning process. This can be seen from the results of data analysis carried out shows the average value of the experimental group ($M_x = 81.93$) while the control group ($M_y = 70.06$). This value shows that the value of M_x is more big in comparison M_y ($81.933 \geq 70.06$). Class VIII students at UPT SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase who used the Lectora application in the learning process did better than students who carried out the learning process without using the Lectora application, according to research findings that compared learning outcomes. Considering students' final exam scores, the findings of these studies can be compared.

Based on the results obtained in the statement above, the hypothesis which states that there is an influence of using the Lectora application on the craft learning outcomes of class VIII UPT SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase students is "accepted". As a consequence of this rejection, the value hypothesis which states that there is no influence of using the Lectora application on learning outcomes in craft subjects for Class VIII students at SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase is rejected. Thus it can be concluded that the Lectora application can have a beneficial impact on learning outcomes in subjects Class craft VII I SMP 3 Pitu Riase. This is shown by student learning outcomes which are quite good when

compared with student learning outcomes where Lectora is not used in learning activities.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the description of the research results regarding the effect of using the Lectora application on the craft learning outcomes of class VIII UPT SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase, it can be concluded that there is an influence of the use of Lectora application on the craft learning outcomes of class VIII UPT SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase students. This indicates that the Lectora application can be used for process learning because media learning based on the Lectora application is very useful for educators and participants alike students in carrying out learning activities that are more interesting and accessible grow interest and motivation. Study for participant educate.

Based on the research results, according to testing the hypothesis through data analysis, the average value was obtained, namely $M_x = 81.933 > M_y = 70.06$. This means that the difference in average scores shows the influence of using the Lectora application on the craft learning outcomes of class VIII UPT SMP Negeri 3 Pitu Riase students. The results of the analysis using the mean formula show that students who learn using the Lectora application have a positive impact compared to students who do not learn using the Lectora application.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "The Impact of the Use of the LECTOR Application on the Subject of Studying the Work of SMPN 3 Pitu Riase."

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